

Supplemental Table 3. Genetic variants represented in Figure 2. Table with 20 columns (A-T) and 324 rows. Columns include variant ID, location, gene, chr, position, ref, var, zygosity, dbSNP ID, MAF (1000 genomes), mutation type, VAF (FTP, LTP, N° of mutation), Qual* (FTP, LTP), Coverage* (FTP, LTP), PP2 Index*, and AAChange*. The table is divided into 'Stable' and 'Progressive' sections. The 'Stable' section contains variants 1-20, and the 'Progressive' section contains variants 21-324. The table includes detailed information for each variant, such as its genomic location, the gene it affects, the specific nucleotide change, its zygosity, and its frequency in the population. It also provides quality scores and coverage metrics for each variant. The 'AAChange*' column indicates the predicted functional effect of the variant on the protein, such as 'frameshift deletion', 'nonsynonymous SNV', 'synonymous SNV', 'frameshift substitution', 'frameshift insertion', and 'stop codon gain'. The 'PP2 Index*' column provides a prediction of the functional effect of the variant on the protein. The 'AAChange*' column indicates the predicted functional effect of the variant on the protein, such as 'frameshift deletion', 'nonsynonymous SNV', 'synonymous SNV', 'frameshift substitution', 'frameshift insertion', and 'stop codon gain'. The 'PP2 Index*' column provides a prediction of the functional effect of the variant on the protein. The 'AAChange*' column indicates the predicted functional effect of the variant on the protein, such as 'frameshift deletion', 'nonsynonymous SNV', 'synonymous SNV', 'frameshift substitution', 'frameshift insertion', and 'stop codon gain'. The 'PP2 Index*' column provides a prediction of the functional effect of the variant on the protein.